

Area Based Childhood Early Numeracy Programme: Numeracy in Action

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The Early Learning Initiative, Area Based Childhood, early numeracy programme aims to improve the educational outcomes for children in developing early maths skills, while increasing parental involvement in children’s learning and development. The working group and pre numeracy planning meetings provide a collaborative space for early years educators and infant class teachers to reflect upon teaching practice and plan for children’s learning. This approach ensures continuity and progression in mathematical learning from home to early years settings and local schools through a playful approach. The purpose of this paper is to present the collaborative work between infant class teachers in primary schools and early childhood educators from the Dublin Dockland and North East Inner City of Dublin.

Introduction

The benefit of learning about maths in early childhood has been well documented through research in Ireland and internationally. Research conducted in Ballymun by O’Kane and Hayes (2010) confirmed this with the participants identifying developing mathematical concepts and the language of Maths, along with oral language, as being the most important skills for children to possess when starting primary school.

In 2005, the Early Learning Initiative commissioned the Dartington Social Research Unit to undertake a community survey to identify the early education needs of the children in the area. Its main finding was that while parents had high aspirations for their children, they did not understand their pivotal role in enhancing their own children’s learning. This finding informed the planning and designing of our programmes. This programme is funded through the Area Based Childhood (ABC) programme.

Parental confidence in helping with maths homework was measured as part of the 2009 *National Assessment of Mathematics and English Reading* (NA 2009) (Eivers et al., 2010). Comparison of its findings with the findings from our recent survey would suggest that parents in the Docklands felt less confident in helping their children than parents nationally. The fact that the NA (2009) found that pupil mean test scores differed significantly by parent confidence, highlights the need for this project. The report also found that parental ratings of their children’s ability tended to be overly positive and indicated that many parents lacked a clear understanding of how their child was performing. It recommended that parents be advised about practices that help their child’s general academic development as well as specific curricular areas. This is very much in line with the needs as identified by the *Dartington Survey* (2006).

Similarly, the PISA Report highlighted that 1 in 6 students in Ireland is poorly prepared for future mathematical needs as students and citizens. Low socioeconomic status (SES) students are more at risk of low achievement, particularly when they attend schools in which large numbers of students are also socioeconomically disadvantaged (Shiel et al.,

2007). The recent *2009 National Assessment of Mathematics and English Reading* (Eivers et al., 2010) also linked low familial SES as an indicator of lower pupil achievement. Given the recent Higher Education Authority *Study on Progression in Higher Education* showing that mathematics is a key predictor of future economic performance and maths-based subjects the trigger for non-completion at third level (HEA 2010), this project is both timely and necessary.

Internationally, research findings highlight the importance of early numeracy as an indicator of future academic success. Examining data from six studies of close to 36,000 pre-schoolers in the United States, Canada and England, researchers found that, having controlled for IQ, family income, gender, temperament, type of previous educational experience, and whether children came from single or two parent families, the mastery of early mathematical concepts on school entry predicted not only future math achievement, it also predicts future reading achievement (Northwestern University, 2007). Interestingly, the opposite -- reading skills predicting mathematical success -- was not significant.

Research in the US (National Academy of Sciences 2009) indicated that opportunities for pre-schoolers to learn mathematics were currently inadequate, particularly for those in low income groups. It found that as mathematical learning was often embedded in other activities and secondary to other learning goals, it was not effective. Giving parents, care givers, early years practitioners and teachers, it argued, the tools to develop and build on children's interests and provide children with high quality Mathematical interactions was the 'foundation for future learning and would help address long-term systematic inequities in educational outcomes'.

The *Draft National Plan to Improve Literacy and Numeracy in Schools* (Department of Education and Skills [DES], 2010b) is in agreement with our consortium in thinking that the teaching and learning of mathematics in Ireland requires even greater attention than literacy. With surveys of mathematics achievement at the primary level, and patterns of participation and achievement in the State examinations and in international surveys, indicating that there are systemic issues in mathematics education that required attention, it argued that system-wide measures are needed to improve the way students engage with mathematics and develop numeracy skills. The numeracy programme provides a prototype of how local communities can promote successful learning, teaching, and assessment in numeracy.

Our consortium has been working together since 2006, with the community action research approach is approved by the National College of Ireland Ethics Committee. Beginning in 2011 with funding from the National Early Years Access Initiative (NEYAI), this programme is aimed at improving early year's numeracy and mathematical skills from birth to six years of age. With funding from the ABC Programme, this programme has grown from 16 organisations and 498 children in 2011/12 to 38 organisations and 1,265 children in 2019/20. The programme revolves around three community Early Numeracy Weeks. There is a different theme each term. The numeracy themes are, Positional Directional Language,

Shape and Space, Counting, Symbols of the Environment, Time, Measurement and Capacity, Money, Number, Sequence and Pattern.

Working group meetings, pre numeracy planning workshops and onsite mentoring support educators in early years services and infant classes in primary schools to reflect on and improve the quality of the programme and their practice using the *Aistear Síolta Practice Guide* as a resource. These meetings have been hosted using virtual online platforms since April 2020 due to the Covid 19 worldwide pandemic.

Numeracy Programme and National Policy

There are two main elements of the numeracy programme which correlate with ‘*First 5, A Whole-of-Government Strategy for Babies, Young Children and their Families (2019-2028)*’. Action area 2- relates to a new model of parenting support which provides guidance to parents to promote healthy behaviours, facilitating positive play-based early learning. The numeracy home-activity cards support capacity building within the home learning environment, supporting parents to realise their potential as their child’s primary educator. This is achieved by providing parents with guidance on key vocabulary words to use when describing their child’s actions during play. This practice promotes a positive play based home learning environment as outlined in Goal three of the strategy.

Building Block 3, refers to a skilled and sustainable workforce, the numeracy programme provides early years educators with the opportunity to share their experiences and reflect upon their learning in the working group meeting and the pre-numeracy workshops. This peer learning provides the opportunity to build capacity within the workforce and develop the quality of the early years educational provision.

The *Department of Education and Skills (2018)* education focused inspections report highlighted the need to build capacity within early years educators to provide high quality educational experiences for children from three years, prior to starting in primary school. The numeracy programme provides a space for educators to reflect upon their practice and plan for developing numeracy educational experiences. Collaboration between early years educators and primary teachers allows the educators to consider how they wish to plan for the learning experiences considering children’s interests and the learning environment. How will families be invited to participate? How will children’s learning opportunities be extended?

Programme Delivery

There were 1,265 children and 1,898 parents involved in the programme overall. The children and parents were predominantly associated with 11 schools, 12 early childhood care services, 5 school age childcare services, five libraries and five health centres. Participants received numeracy cards and activity packs to be used at home and in schools and services.

The service delivery moved onto a virtual platform from March to June 2020 in response to the Covid-19 pandemic. Nine schools, eight early childhood care education services and five school age childcare centres engaged virtually. The libraries actively

promoted the programme on social media. The Early Learning Initiative posted play-based numeracy activities daily on social media as well as links to the numeracy cards. There was a total of 18 numeracy themed posts from March to June with a reach of 20,439 and 1,642 engagements.

Participant Learning and Feedback

On completion of each Early Numeracy Week both staff and parents were asked to provide through an evaluation. In total across the three terms in 2019/2020, 250 parents and 126 staff completed evaluations. Although these figures are both lower than those of 2018/19 (432 and 193 respectively), it must be noted that the lockdown of schools and services in March of 2020 hindered the collection of evaluations for Early Numeracy Weeks 2 and 3. The majority of both staff (89%, n=112) and parents (96%, n=210) agreed or strongly agreed that the Early Numeracy Weeks were an enjoyable experience for the children involved. Ninety-two percent (n=209) of parents also highlighted their own enjoyment in completing the activities with their child.

Staff also reported that the Early Numeracy Weeks provided valuable learning opportunities for the children (91%, n=109), parents (89%, n=105) and staff (82%, n=97). According to staff, the Early Numeracy Weeks improved children's understanding of the numeracy theme (75%, n=94) and increased parental involvement (53%, n=67). Along with enjoyment, parents found the Early Numeracy Weeks encouraged them to become more involved with their child's learning (92%, n=216), talk and play with their child more (88%, n=205) and improve their teaching skills/knowledge (83%, n=191). Parents also reported the Early Numeracy Weeks improved their child's numeracy skills (94%, n=217), provided their children with the opportunity to learn more about numeracy (93%, n=214), improved their child's understanding of each numeracy theme (91%, n=207), and provided their child with the opportunity to spend more quality time with adults (84%, n=190).

Staff reported that the Early Numeracy Weeks positively impacted their own practices and learning, primarily in the areas of learning new ideas for incorporating numeracy into their teaching (29%, n=29), finding ways to make learning numeracy fun (22%, n=22) and gaining a better understanding of the children's abilities (17%, n=17).

Conclusion

The numeracy programme provides the opportunity for infant class primary school teachers and early years educators to work together to improve the educational outcomes for the children they work with. This is a positive peer learning opportunity which benefits children's learning opportunities and capacity building of professionals to reflect upon and build on their practice as educators. The children's needs and interests are placed at the focus of the planning process. The role of the adult is to provide a rich play environment that supports children's early learning and numeracy skills. Community action research supports reflecting upon and building on practice in a collaborative way involving all stakeholders.

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